
A REVIEW OF WEB BASED APPLICATIONS AND INTERFACES FOR INTERNET OF THINGS (IoT) PROJECTS

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ABSTRACT

The use of web-based applications in combined implementation with Internet of Things (IoT) has become rampant in recent years as a result of technological advancement and research. This has enhanced adequate and appropriate monitoring of the functioning of diverse operations for both household (personal) and industrial purposes. IoT refers to the usage of the internet for all functional purposes. IoT devices are used to give people safe, on-demand services in a variety of locations, including our homes, workplaces, malls, schools, airports, and many more. A key component of the Internet of Things is the development of web-based applications which effectively empower consumers through interaction with a range of digital objects. Furthermore, IoT systems are putting several beneficial technology advancements into practice across a range of industries, particularly in web-based applications. A real-time monitoring system that can be interfaced with the Internet of Things is offered by the web-based application. Users may obtain information about and operate linked IoT devices in real time thanks to web-based apps that interface with the Internet of Things.

Keywords: Internet of Things (IoT), web-based application, automation, Internet, technology

1. INTRODUCTION

From only linking computers and mobile devices, the Internet is expanding to include real-world items, becoming the Internet of Things (IoT). The interconnected Internet of things reveals environmental data from these items to the use of sophisticated cloud and Internet apps and systems, which are meant to blur the lines between the real and digital worlds (Mert, 2014). The term "Internet of Things" is widely used in the media to describe a true revolution in the environments in which it is present. This revolution aims to make these environments more intelligent by combining a network of physical objects with electronic components, such as sensors and software, which gather and share data with the user and with each other (Alves et al., 2019).

Internet and mobile communication technologies are becoming more and more integrated into people's everyday routines in today's developing society, especially in useful Internet of Things (IoT) applications (Chen et al., 2024). By altering the way humans and machines communicate with each other through user interfaces, IoT technology brings the digital world together. Now that it has made its way into the realm of web development, the Internet of Things has established a smart and significant position in the market by increasing user contact with websites (Dushyant and Kumudini, 2024). Computer-based, automated systems have been introduced and widely used in recent years to perform a variety of crucial tasks for domestic, business, and personal usage. These processes are simple to manage and monitor. For this reason, it has become quite pertinent for the creation of web-based applications that can give real-time readings of parameters measured; this presents the industrious amalgamation of web-based applications and the Internet of Things.

The Internet of Things (IoT) is the fastest-growing technology, with significant effects on social life and corporate settings due to its recent quick growth and capacity to provide a wide range of services. The proliferation of Internet of Things (IoT) devices and services is happening very quickly. The number of threats and assaults against IoT devices and services is also rising, indicating that their success has not gone unnoticed (Nimodiya and Ajankjar, 2022). IoT encompasses a range of services, applications, and communication technologies, enabling omnipresent tracking and data collecting to deliver intelligent services that can enhance people's lives (Leena, 2020). Internet-based applications, such remote monitoring systems, are growing in popularity in industry due to the Internet's recent rapid expansion. A remote monitoring system enables the user to remotely regulate the situation in real time using a computer or smartphone over the limitless Internet (Kao et al., 2018).

Web-based apps, a crucial part of the Internet of Things (IoT), efficiently assist consumers by interacting with a variety of IoT-based digital devices. IoT-based web technology has revolutionized human existence by enabling connectivity for all people, everywhere, at any time (Alaa et al., 2017). IoT has been growing in popularity lately. Using the web browser as a platform to view the status of the linked items or things has been one method. The network is known as the Web of Things (WoT) when the linked items in the IoT are also included in the World Wide Web. In an IoT system, a centralized hub is often used to control the connected devices. The hub often receives the current sensor outputs from the linked devices and creates commands to regulate different device characteristics. Currently available WoT solutions often do not interact with the web browser; instead, they use the browser simply to access the server's control interface (Kapil et al., 2016).

2. EMPIRICAL REVIEW

The linking of individually identifiable embedded computer devices inside the current Internet infrastructure is known as the Internet of Things (IoT). Beyond machine-to-machine communications, IoT often provides improved connection of devices, systems, and services across a range of protocols, domains, and applications. In almost every area of automation, these embedded devices—including smart objects—are connected to one another, allowing for sophisticated uses such as the Smart Grid. In the context of the Internet of Things, "things" might include anything from implants for heart monitoring to biochip transponders on farm animals, electric mussels in coastal waters, cars with integrated sensors, or field operation tools that help firefighters with search and rescue. Examples from the current market are washers and dryers that use Wi-Fi for remote monitoring and thermostat systems (Aishwarya *et al.*, 2017).

In a study, the phrase "Internet of Things" was first used to describe the combination of Internet-connected sensors, gadgets, and people. According to Guinard *et al.* (2012), a "smart city" is defined as an Internet-connected network of residents (people) and electronic sensors and equipment (things) that can perform a variety of tasks linked to several practical applications that are advantageous to humans. Simple sensors can be easily controlled at advanced automation levels by connecting to a variety of micro-controller platforms. Additionally, transferring sensor data via a smart grid allows for a large volume of data to be collected for precise emergency decision-making. Therefore, by keeping an eye on the equipment's condition, IoT can transform how embedded systems communicate and react for a range of applications, particularly when there is a vulnerability in a particular area of operation. This will enable a prompt, secure, and efficient response for a safer working environment and operations (Zhao *et al.*, 2019).

One advantage of web-based monitoring technology is that it eliminates the need for client-side application architecture. Users can monitor and manage programs by connecting to the webserver via a web browser. Additionally, a cross-platform online monitoring system may be built as long as the site design supports HTML5 (Hypertext Markup Language 5). HTML5 versions are supported by browsers on a variety of operating systems, including PCs, tablets, and smartphones. Thus, managers may monitor systems using portable mobile devices by utilizing web-based monitoring technology that enables simultaneous local and distant cross-platform monitoring systems (Chen *et al.*, 2024).

A low-cost, real-time monitoring system that can be utilized for prompt and precise smart grid monitoring has been created under the Smart Grid Environment. It can also monitor a variety of power system metrics. It entails real-time voltage and current waveform measurements as well as the identification of power system disruptions as they are occurring (Prakash and Subramani, 2016). It offers dedicated utility communication on cellular networks that ensure robust security, dependability with lower operating costs, and good quality for inexpensive maintenance (Granzer, 2010).

Using widely recognized communication protocols, the Internet of Things is a worldwide network of interconnected, individually addressable objects. Recent years have seen great advancements in technology, and this trend is still going strong. In addition to creating innumerable multipurpose technologies, such as blazingly fast computers, smart mobile devices, advanced robotics, self-driving cars, and many more, technological advancements have significantly enhanced human lives. Anyone with a computer, smartphone, wearable technology, washing machine, smart speaker, or other Internet-connected electrical

equipment has heard of the Internet of Things (IoT). Web design and development will be impacted by IoT, among other things (Dushyant and Kumudini, 2024).

Over the past few decades, the Internet has expanded rapidly and widely, from supporting hundreds of hosts to offering billions of intricate, networked hosting options. Due to the increasing number of mobile devices connected to the Internet, the Internet is still evolving quickly. The modern Internet architecture, where individuals are routinely linked to the Internet, is made up of interconnected PCs and mobile devices. Moving beyond linked computers and mobile devices to connected real-world items is the next big step in Internet connection. Therefore, the goal is to expand the Internet of Things to include the Internet of Computers (Mert, 2014).

The concept and execution of Wireless Monitor, a free and adaptable web application for the Internet of Things (IoT), was reported in a paper by Alves et al. (2019). The primary goal of Wireless Monitor is to offer a secure online and real-time data visualization solution. To keep an eye on IoT sensor devices, the user may utilize Wireless Monitor to develop a customized web environment. The gathered data may be shown as real-time charts and is kept on a cloud server databank. Thanks to the system of plugins, the suggested Wireless Monitor has been designed to be expandable and adaptable to other sensor kinds. Because the JSON information exchange protocol only requires a small number of endpoints for information sharing between the server and the IoT device, development is made easier without being constrained. This section presents the findings of two distinct practical trials. In the first, a Raspberry Pi, Arduino, and an LM35 temperature sensor are used; in the second, an ESP 8266 development board is used in place of both embedded systems.

One sophisticated kind of energy meter that can measure and provide data on energy usage in real time is an Internet of Things (IoT)-based smart meter. According to studies, smart meters differ from normal energy meters in that they are equipped with internet of things (IoT) technology, which enables them to connect to other devices over the internet (Tariq et al., 2018). Through the transmission of energy consumption data to utility companies and consumers, IoT-based smart meters offer enhanced energy management and cost-saving strategies. Customers may modify their usage as necessary because they have real-time access to data about their energy consumption. Utility companies can utilize the data to reduce the likelihood of blackouts and brownouts by balancing energy supply and demand (Bouabdallah et al., 2017).

By altering the way humans and machines communicate with one another through user interfaces, the Internet of Things is a technology that brings the digital world together. Now that the Internet of Things has made its way into the realm of web creation, it has established a sophisticated and significant position while also increasing user interaction with websites. Understanding client traits and creating the most effective strategies are made easier by its remarkable computerized sensitivity feature and connectivity strength. The Internet of Things edge in web development will change the frontend user interface and other user interactions. All users will interact with cameras, sensors, and other Internet-connected devices using this front-end interface (Dushyant and Kumudini, 2024).

The Internet of Things (IoT) is a system that enhances information exchange between operators and linked items by fusing sensors, software, electronics, and networking. It reduces the human work by incorporating machine-to-machine interaction. Understanding energy use trends is necessary due to the growing need for energy in daily life. With the growth of IOT, several complex applications for smart cities have offered answers. It is the

ability for networks, sensors, and devices to communicate with one another both in person and virtually. The intelligent infrastructure developed and constructed via the use of IoT technologies, which promote connectivity and interoperability, is a crucial part of the future smart world. IoT technologies are used by energy monitoring systems to enable remote monitoring. Remote monitoring enables efficient, cost-effective data measurement and monitoring (Rabbani et al., 2019).

Anitha (2017) highlights the following as an additional rubbish management strategy. A microcontroller-based system with infrared wireless technologies and a central system that displayed the garbage's present state was interfaced with the bin. Using Wi-Fi, the status was seen on a mobile web browser that displayed an HTML page. They only employed weight-based sensors to cut costs, and they only used a Wi-Fi module on the sender's end to transmit and receive data. Ultimately, the sensor was only able to identify the weight of the garbage in the bin—not its level.

Internet of Things (IoT) is a novel approach that uses state-of-the-art technology to increase the effectiveness and efficiency of several systems. This system uses sensors, controllers, and communication devices to automate and improve the watering process (Puneeth et al., 2023). Pervasive computing, ubiquitous communications, and ambient intelligence are all combined in the Internet of Things. This will provide the basis for a number of new applications, such as energy monitoring, transportation safety systems, and building security. Recent developments in the domains of IoT, Big Data, Cloud, and Mobile Computing are guiding the globe toward more intelligent solutions to real-life problems. Many businesses currently create the hardware elements needed by the Internet of Things, such as sensors with communication modules and control devices with self-networking capabilities (Ratnakumari and Koteswari, 2020).

An IoT ecosystem, according to Nimodiya and Ajankar (2022), is made up of web-enabled smart devices that gather, transmit, and act upon data they receive from their surroundings using embedded systems, such as CPUs, sensors, and communication gear. Connecting to an IoT gateway or another edge device allows IoT devices to exchange the sensor data they gather. From there, the data is either transferred to the cloud for local analysis or stored locally. These gadgets can occasionally talk to other similar gadgets and take action based on the information they exchange. Although people can engage with the devices—for example, to set them up, give them instructions, or retrieve the data—the gadgets perform the majority of the job without human participation.

Through the utilization of sophisticated systems on the Internet, connected items will transport environmental information from the physical world into the digital realm. The majority of items in this category are restricted devices, like sensors or actuators, that are positioned throughout everyday surroundings and have the ability to gather a variety of environmental data, including humidity levels, patient heart rate measurements, room temperature, and many more. Various network entities can process the acquired data, and various applications can be extracted from the information (Mert, 2014). A research on the effects and difficulties of IoT in web development by Dushyant and Kumudini (2024) found that IoT is having a major positive influence on web development. As a result, people's interactions with websites and online apps are evolving. Similar to a gold mine, the Internet of Things (IoT) is the cornerstone of an exciting technological future. IoT has revolutionized almost every industry, from manufacturing to healthcare. Not surprisingly, it has already started to influence the design and development of online apps. Regardless of the front-end software, content management system, or programming language utilized, web development

innovation probably takes primacy in people's everyday employment. Both software companies and individual web developers may benefit greatly from the ongoing expansion of Internet of Things devices on the worldwide market.

Research was conducted by Okafor et al. (2017). This study used interdisciplinary principles in mechatronics to construct an Arduino-based energy consumption rate meter for residential houses. The system uses the composite design methodology (CDM) to provide real-time demand side management. It includes the cluster units for cloud servers and metering. To accomplish the system features, the study presented the Arduino Uno (with ATmega328 chipset), SIM800L GSM modules, and ACS712 Hall Effect current sensor. Direct debugging in the open source Integrated Development Environment (IDE) was made possible by the design description on the editor run-time environment. Usability tests and a few chosen case studies were used to assess the strategy. With the latter, the system's applicability offered a productive way to track energy usage with little mistakes. The findings demonstrated that an output of 0.00kWh was recorded when the meter was turned on without any load. An output of 10.75kWh was then shown on the cloud web application (in real time) after connecting an i-core7 Dell Inspiron laptop to it. As anticipated, the production continued to rise as the load remained attached to the meter.

Numerous IoT device monitoring options are available. In addition to free solutions like Kaa and SiteWhere, some platforms that are worth mentioning include Oracle IoT, AWS IoT, Google Cloud IoT, and Microsoft Azure IoT Suite, which are created by significant corporations like Oracle, Amazon, Google, and Microsoft, respectively (Alves, 2019). Similar possibilities for creating bundles and applications are provided by other technologies such as macchina.io and ThingSpeak, both of which may incorporate graphic visualization and decision-making (Hill, 2019). Applications like Kaa and SiteWhere operate in a Java environment, which increases the cost of deployment since hosting is more expensive than for PHP applications. Additionally, processing power needs to be high because this environment necessitates a more reliable server (Alves, 2019).

The concept of the Internet of Things (IoT) has the potential to fundamentally change how we interact with technology. Science fiction used to hold up the prospect of a future where every technological gadget in our environment is a part of a single, interconnected network. Since the Internet of Things is still in its infancy, the market is concentrating on its vertical domains at the moment. More attention must be paid to interfaces, platforms, mobile apps, and common/dominant standards in order to realize the anticipated rapid development from IoT potential (Nimodiya & Ajankjar, 2022). IoT is a network type that can intelligently program, gather, send, and prepare data or information in addition to connecting infrastructure through a variety of sensing devices and the internet. Additionally, it can carry out scientific management from anywhere at any time. An Internet of Things (IoT)-based energy monitoring system might be developed to enhance energy efficiency and save expenses. The Internet of Things-based energy monitoring system may help with the difficulties of gathering, transmitting, and storing large volumes of data on energy consumption practices by utilizing a variety of assortment strategies (Mohd et al., 2023).

Energy optimization in smart buildings and next-generation building management systems depend on the Internet of Things. To facilitate remote control and monitoring, the system has to employ a few communication protocols (Priyadharshini et al., 2019). The Internet of Things (IoT) is a network of physical items (things) that have been outfitted with sensors, software networks, and other technologies that allow them to connect to and exchange data with other devices or systems over the Internet. Previously inept equipment may now interact

in real time without human aid by linking various devices and integrating sensors. An Internet of Things device might be any physical object that can be controlled online or used to send data to other devices (Iloh et al., 2023). IOT is accomplished by employing local networking standards and leveraging Raspberry Pi and embedded web server technology to remotely manage and monitor industrial device characteristics (Kannappan et al., 2022). The ARM11 CPU and Real Time Operating System make up the Raspberry Pi module, while embedded web server technology combines Internet and embedded device technologies. Industrial equipment may be remotely monitored and controlled using a local web browser when an embedded web server and Raspberry Pi are used.

The Integrated-Sensor Monitoring System (I-SMS) platform was suggested by Yew et al. (2023) and makes use of a variety of IoT sensor nodes, including power meters and temperature and humidity (T/H) sensors. The topology begins with the AC operating and the data being measured appropriately by the IoT sensors. The IoT gateway receives data from the IoT sensors, saves it in JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) format, and then sends the JSON data to the ThingsSentral Cloud application programming interface (API) in POST URL format every ten minutes. The JSON data will be registered into the ThingsSentral database via the API after processing the POST URL. The ThingsSentral platform is an Internet of Things platform that offers a number of features, including the ability to register sensor data, store data in a database, show data in dials or graphs, and monitor data in a personalized performance dashboard. The integrated-sensor monitoring system (I-SMS) provides users with access to the Web GUI for data monitoring, and the performance dashboard allows them to view pertinent chart plots.

An interactive microgrid virtual laboratory centered on teaching about renewable energy is presented by Guo et al. (2022). According to the study, people can comprehend different controls and results of the virtual grid using their web browser, which improves the efficiency of learning about grid systems. The optimal control of robotic arm motions with a Web-based graphical interface is covered by Astudillo et al. (2022). The advantages of web-based monitoring systems are illustrated by these instances. However, extensive training is necessary to develop graphical web design abilities. IBM released Node-RED, a visual programming development tool for building web-based graphical remote monitoring and control systems that work across platforms. IoT systems have made extensive use of it. However, the majority of industrial production equipment may be controlled by programmable logic controllers (PLC). Converting existing equipment into web-based IoT monitoring systems is a crucial research topic.

According to Ali et al. (2019), an Internet of Things application serves as the foundation for the construction of a smart, green home automation environment with appliance monitoring systems. Using the Raspberry Pi as a server system and Wi-Fi as a communication protocol, the study aimed to operate household appliances using smartphones. Here, a web-based interface over the internet allows the user to interact directly with the system. In addition to monitoring sensor data, the developed system also initiates a procedure based on the requirements. Therefore, a Raspberry Pi micro-controller board, a web connection, and relay switches are used to develop globally accessible automation of electronic appliances in a user-friendly manner that allows users to operate household electronic equipment with a high degree of flexibility and security.

3. Overview of IoT Platforms

Internet of Things (IoT) platforms are cloud-based or web-based services that serve as the bridge between IoT devices and applications. These platforms enable the collection, processing, visualization, and control of data generated by connected devices like sensors, actuators, and microcontrollers. IoT platforms provide essential tools such as device management, real-time data analytics, dashboard creation, remote control, and integration with other services like AI, cloud storage, and automation workflows. With the growing number of IoT devices worldwide, these platforms play a crucial role in scaling, securing, and simplifying the development and deployment of IoT solutions.

Whether you're a beginner or a professional, IoT platforms like Blynk, Arduino Cloud, ThingSpeak, and Azure IoT Hub make it easier to build smart projects across various domains such as home automation, health monitoring, agriculture, and industrial control systems. Here are six powerful platforms every budding IoT developer should explore:

3.1 Blynk IoT Platform

Figure 1: Blynk IoT Web Home Page

Why It Stands Out:

- i. Blynk is a drag-and-drop interface that allows you to create beautiful mobile apps for IoT projects in minutes without writing a single line of Android or iOS code!
- ii. It supports ESP8266, ESP32, Arduino, NodeMCU, and more.
- iii. You can control relays, view sensor data, and even receive notifications right from your phone.
- iv. Uses virtual pins to simplify data communication.
- v. Free tier is generous for basic use, and paid plans enable commercial-grade applications.

The Blynk IoT platform is used for projects such as: Home automation, smart agriculture, motion detection systems, and student prototypes.

Blynk IoT Dashboard Interface

Blynk offers a web-first dashboard with a drag-and-drop interface for adding widgets like buttons, sliders, gauges, graphs, and LEDs. Widgets are assigned to virtual pins, making it easy to connect them to microcontroller values. The new Blynk console (web version) supports web dashboards too, with customizable layouts. Users can also set up real-time graphs, notifications, and device control features directly from the app. The figure below shows a typical blynk dashboard.

Figure 2: Sample of Blynk IoT dashboard Interface

3.2 Arduino IoT Cloud

Figure 3: Arduino Cloud Web Home Page

Why It Stands Out:

- i. Developed by the Arduino team, it's tailored for those already familiar with Arduino boards.
- ii. It supports real-time monitoring, automatic device recognition, dashboard creation, and Amazon Alexa integration.
- iii. You can program your board directly from the Arduino Web Editor, making it a complete ecosystem.

- iv. Features include over-the-air (OTA) updates, variable synchronization, and IFTTT-style automation.

The Arduino IoT Cloud is used for projects such as: Smart gardens, temperature monitoring, and voice-controlled home devices.

Arduino IoT Cloud Dashboard Interface

Arduino IoT Cloud provides a clean, responsive web-based dashboard where you can easily drag in widgets to match your device's variables (like temperature, switch state, or humidity). Widgets automatically sync with variables declared in your code using `ArduinoCloudThingProperties.h`, making updates seamless. It supports toggle switches, percentage meters, charts, and status indicators. The dashboard is cloud-synced and mobile-friendly too. The figure below shows a typical Arduino Cloud Dashboard.

Figure 4: Arduino Cloud Web Dashboard Interface

3.3 ThingSpeak

Figure 5: ThingSpeak Web Home Page

Why It Stands Out:

- i. Owned by MathWorks, it has strong integration with MATLAB for advanced data analysis.
- ii. Easy to use with ESP8266, ESP32, Raspberry Pi, and Arduino.
- iii. Allows you to create public or private channels, visualize real-time data in charts, and run MATLAB code for insights.
- iv. You can trigger alerts and webhooks based on custom conditions.

ThingSpeak is used for projects such as: Environmental monitoring, research papers, smart weather stations.

ThingSpeak Dashboard Interface

ThingSpeak's dashboard is structured around "Channels" with fields that can be visualized using widgets like line plots, bar charts, gauges, and maps. The interface is not drag-and-drop but uses a configuration-style setup for each chart. It's especially useful for displaying time-series data from sensors. Widgets are customizable in terms of axis range, colors, titles, and data intervals, and you can embed them on external websites. The figure below shows a typical ThingSpeak Dashboard.

Figure 6: ThingSpeak Web Dashboard Interface

3.4 Microsoft Azure IoT Hub

Figure 7: Azure IoT Hub Web Home Page

Why It Stands Out:

- i. Part of Microsoft Azure, it provides secure communication between billions of IoT devices and cloud services.
- ii. Offers device-to-cloud telemetry, cloud-to-device commands, and bi-directional communication.
- iii. You can integrate AI, Machine Learning, Power BI, and logic apps to create intelligent systems.
- iv. Supports multiple protocols like MQTT, AMQP, and HTTPS.

The Microsoft Azure IoT Hub is used for projects such as: Smart cities, industrial IoT, energy monitoring, and healthcare systems.

Azure IoT Hub Dashboard Interface

Azure IoT Hub itself doesn't offer a visual dashboard but integrates with Azure IoT Central and Power BI for advanced dashboards. Using IoT Central, you can design dashboards with tiles, charts, KPIs, device groups, and telemetry graphs. Widgets are highly customizable and support real-time updates. With Power BI integration, you can perform deep analytics and interactive visualizations, perfect for enterprise-grade monitoring.

Figure 8: Azure IoT Hub Web Dashboard Interface

3.5 Adafruit IO

Figure 9: Adafruit Web Home Page

Why It Stands Out:

- i. Created by Adafruit Industries, it is easy to use and ideal for beginners.
- ii. You can create interactive dashboards, feed data from microcontrollers, and trigger webhooks.
- iii. Compatible with ESP8266, ESP32, Raspberry Pi, and Feather boards.
- iv. Free tier is generous and ideal for learning.

The Adafruit IOs used for projects such as: IoT-based wearables, smart pet feeders, and DIY maker projects.

Adafruit IO Dashboard Interface

Adafruit IO features a modular dashboard builder where users can drag and drop widgets like line charts, toggle buttons, sliders, and indicators. Each widget connects to a “feed” that stores your device’s data. Dashboards are simple, beginner-friendly, and visually pleasing. Adafruit also allows widget sharing and access control, making it ideal for classroom or collaborative projects

Figure 10: Adafruit Web Dashboard Interface

3.6 Ubidots

Figure 11: Ubidot Web Home Page

Why It Stands Out:

- i. Offers real-time data visualization, event alerts, webhooks, and machine learning integration.
- ii. Has a sleek, professional dashboard ideal for businesses and advanced makers.
- iii. Integrates easily with Arduino, Particle, Raspberry Pi, ESP32, and many more.
- iv. Offers email, SMS, Telegram, and Slack notifications.

The Ubidots is used for projects such as: Factory automation, smart inventory, asset tracking systems.

Ubidots Dashboard Interface

Ubidots provides a powerful, responsive dashboard designer with drag-and-drop widgets such as gauges, bar charts, tables, switches, status indicators, and maps. Widgets connect to device variables and can show real-time or historical data. Ubidots stands out for its professional-looking dashboards, automation rules (events), and alerting system. The platform is great for commercial or industrial-grade IoT systems. The figure below shows a typical Ubidot dashboard.

Figure 12: Ubidot Web Dashboard Interface

Comparison Table: IoT Platforms Performance for Beginners

The table below shows a comprehensive comparison that analyzes the six IoT platforms in terms of performance for beginners, focusing on ease of use, dashboard design, device integration, learning curve, documentation, and ideal use cases.

Table 1: IoT Platform Comparison Table

Feature	Platform					
	Blynk IoT	Arduino IoT Cloud	ThingSpeak	Azure IoT Hub	Adafruit IO	Ubidots
Ease of Use	Very Easy (5 Star Rating)	Beginner Friendly (4 Star Rating)	Moderate 3 Star Rating	Complex Setup (2 Star Rating)	Simple UI (4 Star Rating)	Friendly UX (4 Star Rating)
Dashboard Design	Drag & Drop Mobile/Web	Drag & Drop Web	Form-based charts	Tiles via IoT Central	Drag & Drop Web	Drag & Drop Web
Widget Variety	Buttons, sliders, graphs, gauges	Switches, meters, charts	Charts, gauges	KPIs, tiles, graphs	Sliders, toggles, plots	Gauges, charts, maps
Learning Curve	Very low	Low	Medium	High	Low	Medium
Mobile App Support	Native app	Web-responsive	Web only	Not direct	Mobile-friendly	Responsive
Documentation	Well-documented	Beginner-focused	Academic-level docs	Extensive, but pro-level	Clear examples	Rich docs & videos
Cloud Integration	Limited	Alexa, Google	MATLAB, API	Full Azure ecosystem	IFTTT, Webhooks	Webhooks, API
Best Use Case	Quick IoT apps, home automation	Smart devices, school projects	Sensor research, graphing	Industry, enterprise apps	Maker projects, DIY	Commercial IoT apps
Free Plan Availability	Yes	Yes	Yes	Limited tier	Yes	Limited free tier

4. CONCLUSION

The demand for a bridge connecting objects to the Internet is increasing as the Internet of Things develops. Gaining knowledge about this new trend is crucial. By reviewing relevant academic works that touch on web-based apps and their interaction with Internet of Things designs, this article seeks to provide such insights. IoT is a technology that has made life easier and will keep doing so. For more than 20 years, the Internet of Things has been a very active research and development field. Additionally, this study evaluated earlier research that illustrated the development of a platform that allows users to remotely operate a variety of IoT devices.

Science fiction used to hold up the prospect of a future where every technological gadget in our environment is a part of a single, interconnected network. However, IoT is sweeping the globe and has not just made its way into the nonfiction space. In order to protect users' privacy when using IoT devices, it is crucial to provide a platform that allows users to interact directly with their devices and manage them easily from different locations at any time. This is due to the increasing advancements in Internet of Things (IoT) technology, which combines a variety of devices with distinct functions, capabilities, and communication protocols. Consequently, IoT-based web technology has transformed human life by making it possible for everyone to be connected, everywhere, at any time; therefore, research on the above is highly encouraged among scientists, technologists, students and researchers.

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